

3D Computer Vision for Real Time Sprayer Adjustments

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INTRODUCTION

Plant protection product (PPP) savings of up to 25% in specialty crops have been demonstrated by well-adjusted spraying technology like the *Smartomizer H₃O* (Berger *et al.* 2019, Berger *et al.* 2022). Nevertheless, the *Green Deal* with its *Farm-to-Fork* strategy has set the objective of 50% reduction in use of hazardous pesticides by 2030. Hence, high-end smart spraying technology is dearly needed to address growers' environmental and productive challenges. Fede's *AIs* system (pronounced "eyes") jumps-in to fill the void. *AIs* is a comprehensive agronomic solution based on computer vision and *Artificial Intelligence (AI)* that allows to sense the canopy with 3D cameras. In the sequel, the visual inputs, with a well-balanced degree of detail and temporal resolution, provide exact information on crop dimensions, which facilitate real time sprayer adjustments to perform high precision PPP spraying and foliar fertilization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The *AIs* system, as indicated in Fig. 1, is fitted on a tractor and contains two stereo vision cameras per side. Mounting *AIs* on the tractor enables sprayer-independent crop statistics collection. However, collecting data with "*AIs on the Ground*" also bears significant technical challenges, *e.g.* the timing for spray nozzle actuation is dependent on information captured from another vehicle, with sprayer and tractor only loosely coupled. Further, establishing a reliable high-speed data connection between vehicles that get frequently disconnected and reconnected under harsh conditions is a challenge. *AIs* here provides a robust Ethernet solution. Moreover, the issue of keeping camera lenses clean is addressed with a pressurised air-curtain system that shields off the lenses from dust, rain, *etc.* Pressurised air is also used to cool cameras and *AIs*' edge processing unit.

The data collected can be directly used to act on the sprayer, *e.g.* to open and close spray nozzles as a function of detected tree dimensions. To do so, sprayers have to be "*AIs-enabled*", which means, they need an Ethernet connection into the *Sprayer Control System (SCS)* over which to receive proprietary *AIs* commands, and they must be fitted with actuators, *i.e.* the *Nozzle Control Unit (NCU)*, to open and close individual nozzles while maintaining spray pressure constant.

The baseline sprayer was a *Smartomizer H₃O Q_i* of 2000 l, with $n = 26$ identical individual switchable nozzles, $n/2$ per side. The flow rate per nozzle q is calculated as in (Świechowski *et al.* 2012), *i.e.* $q = (Q \cdot R \cdot v) / (600 \cdot n)$, where Q is the *desired spray volume* in l/ha, R is the *interrow distance* in m, and v is the *driving velocity* in km/h.

Test results are obtained in a traditional orange grove, a.) configuring the sprayer in a conventional way selecting the base line Q with respect to the *Tree Row Volume* (Świechowski *et al.* 2012), and b.) allowing *AIs* to switch individual nozzles on and off for segments of the canopy where no foliar content is detected. Opening and closing times are logged, and the time during which the nozzles are closed is subtracted from the total time, which is identical between treatment (a) and (b). To assure no negative impact of *AIs* on

Fig. 1. Fede AIs system embedded into the Fede Specialty Crops Platform (SCP).

distribution and deposition, hydro sensible paper is distributed over the canopy, putting especial emphasis on areas close to canopy holes where AIs is supposed to switch nozzles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Visual inspection of the hydro sensible paper under case (a) and (b) revealed comparable spray distribution and deposition. Comparison of the total of the nozzle opening times between case (a) and (b) revealed a spray volume reduction of up to 40% when using the AIs. This means that with AIs in operation the performed treatment is “equivalent to” a spray volume of $Q_{baseline}$, being in fact apt to save up to 40% of Plant Protection Product (PPP) in the particular situation under test.

While AIs has been demonstrated to work well in this particular context, it should be noted that the effectively achievable savings depend on the variability of the canopy. In very heterogeneous canopies with little holes, less PPP will be saved, while in highly variable canopies with holes or even entire trees missing, savings can be very significant.

These results indicate that the latest advances in Specialty Crops sprayer developments allow growers to significantly reduce their production costs due to PPP inputs savings in line with EU objectives, and contributing to the transition to a net zero agriculture that sustainably delivers food security to the world population.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

With funding of the European Union’s LIFE Programme, the EU’s funding instrument for the environment and climate action GA 101074540 - LIFE21-ENV-ES-Life-AIs.